

INTERNATIONAL INSTITUTE OF RURAL RECONSTRUCTION

The background of the cover is a photograph of a rural landscape. In the foreground, there is a lush green field of young corn plants. The middle ground shows a valley with more greenery and some trees. In the background, there are rolling hills and mountains under a bright, slightly cloudy sky. The overall scene is peaceful and rural.

MYANMAR
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ACTION RESEARCH REPORT: INCREMENTAL COMMUNITY BASED ADAPTATION IN THE HIGHLANDS OF MYANMAR, CHIN STATE

Authors: Barbon WJ, Myae C, Thant PS, Bernardo EB, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/116117>

NURTURING RESILIENCE IN SMALLHOLDER FARMING SYSTEMS: EMERGING INSIGHTS FROM A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE IN SOUTHERN SHAN STATE, MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-07-03

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108682>

RESTORING DRYLANDS, STRENGTHENING RESILIENCE: INSIGHTS FROM A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE IN HTEE PU, NYAUN OO, MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-07-03

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108683>

NURTURING ADAPTATION CAPACITIES IN CHIN HIGHLANDS. LESSONS FROM SAKTA: A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE IN MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-12

Link: <http://bit.ly/3hFpG2s>

PROMOTING NUTRITION IN CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE

Authors: Itliong, Kirstein; Valdemoro, Camille; Calica, Michelle Jeanne; Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-08-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/109055>

NUTRITION CO-BENEFITS OF CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE IN MYANMAR

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction; CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security

Date: 2020-01-08

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107814>

RESOURCE CONSERVATION IN THE UPLANDS OF SOUTHERN SHAN: HOW CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE CAN HELP

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99501>

REGENERATING DRYLANDS IN RESPONSE TO A CHANGING CLIMATE

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99496>

DIVERSIFICATION: REDUCING RISKS, INCREASING INCOMES WHILE ENHANCING ADAPTIVE CAPACITIES IN THE AYEYARWADY DELTA

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99494>

CAPITALIZING ON LOCAL LIVELIHOOD DIVERSITY: ENHANCING RESILIENCE BUILDING OF SMALL HIGHLAND FARMS

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99491>

INTEGRATING GENDER DIMENSIONS IN THE MYANMAR CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES

Authors: Dayo H, Barbon WJ, Thant PS, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115854>

SCALING OF CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE VIA CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN SOUTHEAST ASIA: INSIGHTS AND LESSONS FROM VIETNAM, LAOS, PHILIPPINES, CAMBODIA AND MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon WJ, Punzalan B, Wassman R, Bui VL, Vidallo R, Villanueva J, Talsma T, Bayot R, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115833>

COVID-19 IMPACT ON LOCAL AGRI-FOOD SYSTEM IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: FINDINGS FROM A RAPID ASSESSMENT

Authors: Espino A, Itliong K, Ruba CD, Thy O, Barbon WJ, Monville-Oro E, Gummadi S, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113843>

LOCAL FOOD SYSTEMS IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: PERSPECTIVE FROM THE LOCAL COMMUNITIES

Authors: Espino, Apple; Monville-Oro, Emily; Barbon, Wilson John; Ruba, Christine Dianne; Gummadi, Sridhar; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2021-05-28

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113826>

THE PROMOTION OF CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES TO SUPPORT COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION PROGRAMMING IN MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson J.; Vidallo, Rene; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2017-09-07

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/83372>

FINANCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS FROM FRUIT TREES IN MYANMAR'S CENTRAL DRY ZONE: CASE STUDY FROM HTEE PU CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE

Authors: Manilay A, Barbon WJ, Cabriole MA, Myae C, Thant PS, Gummadi S, Monville-Oro E, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-07

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/114390>

TRAINING ON ESTABLISHING CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES (CSVs) IN MYANMAR TO IMPROVE FOOD SECURITY AND RESILIENCE IN AGRICULTURE

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2019-06-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107415>

CLIMATE AND NUTRITION-SMART VILLAGES AS PLATFORMS TO ADDRESS FOOD INSECURITY IN MYANMAR: FINAL PROJECT END REPORT

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John, Myae, Chan, Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2021-07-15

Link: <https://bit.ly/3lZwSsR>

BUILDING ADAPTIVE CAPACITIES OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES: STORIES OF CHANGE FROM THE CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN MYANMAR

Authors: Myae C, Lian AV, Khar SN, Myint O, & Barbon WJ

Date: 2021-05

Link: <https://bit.ly/3kJUbrd>

CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE OPTIONS FOR MYANMAR SMALL-HOLDER FARMERS: EDUCATION AND TRAINING POSTERS FOR VILLAGES

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

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frontiers in Climate Change

Applying Participatory Action Research Methods in Community-Based Adaptation With Smallholders in Myanmar

Barbon Wilson John, Myae Chan, Vidallo Rene, Thant Phyu Sin, Monville-Oro Emilita and Gonsalves Julian

The effects of climate change to agriculture being largely localized, specific, it is crucial that adaptation measures recognize the value of integrated, context-specific, community-based strategies and processes. The present research participatory action research taking as a broader range of socio-technical methods for facilitating community-based adaptation in climate smart villages. Multifaceted areas in four village agro-ecotypes in Myanmar were targeted. Results and insights from the case participatory action research and community-based adaptation research approach were implemented in the four targeted climate smart villages (CSVs). The two support systems needed to enhance community engagement in understanding the climate are discussed. Sociolearning helped farmers' capabilities to find solutions and address on-farm and on-farm adaptation options, using a combination of socio-technical processes, sustainable farmers, researchers, and facilitators improved the understanding of climate change, extent of vulnerability, and coping strategies. With the knowledge and understanding, the farmers in the CSVs identified a menu of adaptation options that they would test and adopt first-hand. This "bottom-up" approach to testing adaptation options ensures that there were opportunities for men, women, and antibiotic households to participate in the community adaptation process. This approach allowed farmers to determine what was best for them and their families, both approaches further improved adaptation and associated socio-economic welfare. The research suggests that men and women influence the value of the adaptation options and that overall uptake. In villages with high incidence of landlessness, the adaptation options were tested by households. The small group of men and women households identified. A more secure for men and women farmers with less land to engage in diversified and crop production systems. Finally, and most levels of households were other factors influencing the uptake of adaptation options, including those related to changing production for reduced risk.

Keywords: participatory approaches, Myanmar, community-based adaptation, climate, crop, agriculture, climate smart villages, socio-technical processes, participatory action research, adaptation options

APPLYING PARTICIPATORY ACTION RESEARCH METHODS IN COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION WITH SMALLHOLDERS IN MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John, Myae, Chan, Vidallo, Rene, Thant, Phyu Sin, Monville-Oro, Emilita and Gonsalves, Julian

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climate

Community-Level Impacts of Climate-Smart Agriculture Interventions on Food Security and Dietary Diversity in Climate-Smart Villages in Myanmar

Hanley Andrew, Brychkova Galina, Barbon Wilson John, Noe Su Myat, Myae Chan, Thant Phyu Sin, McKeown Peter, Gonsalves Julian

Myanmar's Program on Climate Change, Agriculture & Food Security (MCCAFS), Myanmar and Climate Change (MCCAFS) is a joint program of the Myanmar Ministry of Environmental Conservation and Forestry (MEECF) and the Myanmar Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Irrigation (MALI). The program aims to improve the resilience of Myanmar's agricultural sector to climate change and to improve the livelihoods of smallholder farmers. The program is implemented in four climate-smart villages (CSVs) in Myanmar. The program includes interventions in crop production, livestock production, and post-harvest management. The program also includes interventions in community-based adaptation (CBA) and climate change education. The program is implemented in four climate-smart villages (CSVs) in Myanmar. The program includes interventions in crop production, livestock production, and post-harvest management. The program also includes interventions in community-based adaptation (CBA) and climate change education.

Keywords: climate-smart agriculture, food security, dietary diversity, climate-smart villages (CSVs), MEECF, MALI

COMMUNITY-LEVEL IMPACTS OF CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE INTERVENTIONS ON FOOD SECURITY AND DIETARY DIVERSITY IN CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN MYANMAR

Authors: Hanley, Andrew.; Brychkova, Galina.; Barbon, Wilson John; Noe, Su Myat; Myae, Chan; Thant, Phyu Sin Thant; McKeown, Peter.; Gonsalves, Julian; Spillane, Charles

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Environmental and Sustainability Indicators

Myanmar local food systems in a changing climate: Insights from multiple stakeholders

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ARTICLE INFO

ABSTRACT

Understanding the impact of climate on food systems is vital in identifying the most effective food system interventions. This study aims to explore the impact of climate change on local food systems in Myanmar. The study is based on a participatory action research approach involving multiple stakeholders. The study identifies the most effective food system interventions to address the impact of climate change on local food systems in Myanmar. The study is based on a participatory action research approach involving multiple stakeholders. The study identifies the most effective food system interventions to address the impact of climate change on local food systems in Myanmar.

1. Introduction

Climate change is a global challenge that is affecting food systems in Myanmar. The impact of climate change on local food systems is a complex issue that requires a multi-stakeholder approach. This study aims to explore the impact of climate change on local food systems in Myanmar. The study is based on a participatory action research approach involving multiple stakeholders. The study identifies the most effective food system interventions to address the impact of climate change on local food systems in Myanmar.

MYANMAR LOCAL FOOD SYSTEMS IN A CHANGING CLIMATE: INSIGHTS FROM MULTIPLE STAKEHOLDERS

Authors: Phyu Sin Thant, Apple Espino, Giulia Soria, Chan Myae, Edgard Rodriguez, Wilson John Barbon, Julian Gonsalves

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